

Firstlings: Early Results on Attitudes towards Animals in Early Modern Dutch Texts

Introduction

“Cut three first-born dogs in pieces; put them in a glazed earthen pot, add one and a half pounds of living worms, after they have first been washed in clean water. After having poured six pounds of olive oil on it, and having closed the pot well, you will boil it all in a bain-marie the whole day”, such is the advice of the *Huishoudeleyk woordboek*, a popular 18th century encyclopedia for readers who are experiencing problems with their nerves or joints. The oil that results from this procedure would, after some additional twists and turns, work wonders for the diseased body parts (Chomel, 1743; translation by author). Quite a different approach towards animals is displayed in “De braave sleepersknecht”, a song published in *Economische Liedjes*, a 1781 book by the famous writing duo Wolff and Deken. In this song, a man emphatically expresses his unwillingness to beat a horse. Though his peers laugh, he won't be persuaded, as he closely associates the horse's feelings with his own: “I often think: // Bles is just like me; // Give me a friendly word, // Then I will do almost everything as they should be done” (Wolff & Deken, 1781; translation by author). In the song, the horse is given a name (“Bles”), presumably to present a more human representation of the horse. To modern readers, cutting up three dogs for a cure seems inhumane, while humanizing a horse aligns more with today's values.

As these brief examples illustrate, attitudes towards animals, as derived from textual representations, have changed over time. In a period where reports on climate change and biodiversity loss are getting increasingly alarming (IPBES, 2021; IPCC, 2022), this is not a trivial observation. The change in representation reflects a change in attitude, and likely also a change in treatment of animals. Knowledge about this process can help navigating the bio crises of our time. The goal of our research is to find answers to the fundamental question: how have Dutch attitudes towards animals changed over time? Here, we look at a time frame that has been constitutional to modern societal norms and behavior: the Early Modern Period. We present early results, not showing the attitudinal changes over time yet, but focusing on giving a proof of the technological, methodological principle for the pipeline we developed in order to chart attitudinal changes in the next stage of the research.

In short, we present (1) a pipeline to study historical attitudes towards nature at scale; (2) proof of concept, showing that this pipeline registers various, very distinctive attitudes towards animals in the cited Early Modern Dutch texts; (3) we embed this technological, methodological work in a theoretical framework connected to Environmental Humanities, demonstrating how to implement digital and computational methods in such a field.

Theoretical Framework

Point of departure for this framework is the substantial amount of research on Early Modern attitudes towards animals that has been conducted since the 1980's. In *Man and the Natural World* (1984), Keith Thomas describes Early Modern England as a period of change. In the sixteenth century, animals were regarded in a purely utilitarian or exploitative way. From the late 17th century, urbanization and modern science spurred new attitudes, including moralistic and affectionate ones. In *Perceiving Animals, Humans and Beasts in Early Modern English Culture* (2000), Erica Fudge examines the demarcation lines humans try to place between themselves and animals. Fudge suggests these show fragility in the Early Modern period. Based on Thomas' and Fudge's findings in an English context, a change in attitudes towards animals during the Early Modern period can be hypothesized for the Netherlands also.

To be able to study this computationally, and thus to operationalize current theses that have only been explored with non-computational means, we use Stephen Kellert's *relational values in social-*

ecological systems (Kellert, 1984). The idea of relational values is connected with the biophilia hypothesis, which holds that humans have innate urge to connect with their natural surroundings (Wilson, 1984). The theory of relational values puts forward a typology of ten attitudinal categories that it assumes to be universal: attraction, dominionistic, reason, affection, moralistic, naturalistic, aversion, spiritual, symbolic, and exploitation (Ross et al., 2018). In their attitude towards nature, humans display these attitudes. The theory is strongly founded and tested in long-term empirical research (Ross et al., 2018), which suggests that it is applicable to historical literature too. This theory provides a solid analytical model for our computational research.

Methods

This theory is combined with recent developments in Natural Language Processing (NLP). First we trained a custom GysBERT model (Manjavacas & Fonteyn, 2022) to find occurrences of nature in Dutch texts, following an indirect annotation strategy (Van Dalfsen et al., 2024). The model identified explicit mentions of animals in historical texts taken from the DBNL database (digital library for Dutch literary texts; Koninklijke Bibliotheek, 2024). For this specific classification task, the model achieved an F1-score of 0.87, demonstrating its effectiveness in reliably identifying relevant textual elements.

Identified sentences were then categorized by means of an decoder model (gpt-4o). The model is prompted to summarize the sentence, confirm the presence of animals, produce a reasoning step for what relational value (if any) is the most dominant in the sentence, and then output the relational value in such a way that is easy to post-process. The decoder model replaces human labeling at scale (Bamman et al., 2024), an approach that has been shown by Karjus (2023) to be promising for this type of tasks. On a test set, the model-derived annotations are in agreement with human annotations in 67% of the cases.

Afterwards, the attitudes extracted from the texts can be used for further analysis, such as line graphs illustrating the prevalence of certain attitudes over time or radar plots visualizing the distribution of attitudes within specific texts. A schematic representation of the pipeline employed in this process is presented in Figure 1.

Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of our method, we applied it on the two texts cited in the introduction. As is evident from the selected quotes, the first text predominantly reflects an exploitative attitude, while the second shows signs of non-exploitative attitudes, such as affection.

Figure 2, shows radar plots of the attitudes found in both texts. *Huishoudlyk Woordboek* shows exploitation as the dominant attitude, with dominion and reason also being present. In contrast, *Economische Liedjes* also features exploitation, but it is less dominant, and has a more diverse distribution of attitudes. A symbolical attitude (where the animals are used to express some meaning) is almost as dominant as exploitation, and attraction, affection, moralistic (emphasizing

Figure 1 Schematic representation of pipeline to extract attitudes towards animals from textual data

the human duty towards animals), and naturalism (an attitude where one “merges” with the animal) are present too.

Figure 2 Radar plots for “*Huishoudelyk woordboek*” (left) and “*Economische Liedjes*” (right). The plots show the frequency of relational values towards animals in both texts. The ID-codes refer to the texts’ identifiers in DBNL.

Conclusion and discussion

The proposed method successfully identifies the expected attitudinal differences between these two texts. *Huishoudelyk Woordboek* is predominantly exploitative, while *Economische Liedjes* shows a more diverse palette of attitudes, including affection. These findings align with the impressions derived from the quotes in the introduction and our broader familiarity with these texts. We interpret this as proof of concept for the proposed method’s effectiveness.

The results of this study are preliminary. To conduct this study, we used an encoder model from an earlier study, trained for finding multiple types of nature. A model specifically designed for the task of attitude detection is expected to achieve higher accuracy. For the decoder model, we did no systematic prompt optimization study; agreement with human judgement is expected to be higher if such a study is done. It is important to note that this task inherently involves a degree of subjectivity, as even two human annotators may disagree on the classification. The inherent ambiguity resulting from this fact can be estimated by comparing two human annotators, but this comparison was not performed in the current study. Lastly, we chose Kellert’s framework of relational values because it is an empirically tested framework that takes a comprehensive approach; to our knowledge Kellert’s framework is unique in this regard, but the existence of alternatives should be studied further. In the near future, we intend to address these limitations and refine our approach in subsequent research.

Notwithstanding the clear points of improvement, these preliminary results present a proof of concept for our method to extract nature attitudes from historical text. This study can thus be seen as a firstling of the flock: while still in its infancy, it holds a promise of growth to something substantial, in this case a method to track developments in human attitudes towards animals over large periods of time, connecting environmental humanities questions with methods from the digital and computational humanities.

References

- Bamman, D., Chang, K.K., Lucy, L. & Zhou, N. (2024). On Classification with Large Language Models in Cultural Analytics. *Proceedings of the Computational Humanities Research Conference 2024*, 494-527. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3834/>
- Chomel, N. (1743). *Huishoudeelyk woordboek, Vervattende vele middelen om zyn goed te vermeederen, en zyne gezondheid te behouden, Met verscheiden wisse en beproefde middelen* (J.L. Schuer & A.H. Westerhof, Translators; N. van der Sijs, Editor). S. Luchtmans/H. Uytwerf. (Original work published 1709). https://www.dbnl.org/tekst/chom003huis01_01/
- Dalfsen, A. van, Karsdorp, F., Bagheri, A., Mentink, D., Engelen, T. van & Stronks, E. Direct and Indirect Annotation with Generative AI: A Case Study into Finding Animals and Plants in Historical Text. *Proceedings of the Computational Humanities Research Conference 2024*, 1053-1074. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3834/>
- Fudge, E. (2000). *Perceiving animals: Humans and beasts in early modern English culture*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-62415-7>
- IPBES (2019). Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. (In S. Díaz, J. Settele, E. S. Brondízio, H. T. Ngo, M. Guèze, J. Agard, A. Arneeth, P. Balvanera, K. A. Brauman, S. H. M. Butchart, K. M. A. Chan, L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii, J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, G. F. Midgley, P. Miloslavich, Z. Molnár, D. Obura, A. Pfaff, S. Polasky, A. Purvis, J. Razzaque, B. Reyers, R. Roy Chowdhury, Y. J. Shin, I. J. Visseren-Hamakers, K. J. Willis, and C. N. Zayas (eds.)). IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553579>
- IPCC. (2022). Summary for policymakers. In H. O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E. S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösche, V. Möller, A. Okem, & B. Rama (Eds.), *Climate change 2022: impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the sixth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Karjus, A. (2023). Machine-assisted mixed methods: augmenting humanities and social sciences with artificial intelligence. arXiv preprint <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.14379>. 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.14379>.
- Kellert, S. R. (1984). American attitudes toward and knowledge of animals: An update. In M. W. Fox & L. D. Mickley (Eds.), *Advances in animal welfare science 1984/85* (pp. 177–213). Washington, DC: The Humane Society of the United States.
- Koninklijke Bibliotheek (2024). Digitale Bibliotheek voor de Nederlandse Letteren (DBNL). Collectie publiek domein. <https://www.dbnl.org/letterkunde/pd/index.php>
- Manjavacas, E. & Fonteyn, L. (2022). Non-parametric word sense disambiguation for historic languages. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Natural Language Processing for Digital Humanities*, 123-134. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.nlp4dh-1.16>
- Ross, H., Witt, K., & Jones, N. A. (2018). Stephen Kellert's development and contribution of relational values in social-ecological systems. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 35, 46–

53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.10.007>

Thomas, K. (1991). *Man and the natural world: Changing attitudes in England 1500-1800* (New ed.). London, UK: Penguin Books Ltd.

Wilson, E. O. (1984). *Biophilia*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Wolff, B. & Deken, A. (1781). *Economische liedjes*. Isaac van Cleef.
https://www.dbnl.org/tekst/wolf016econ01_01/